

**THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE - MODERN CHALLENGES AND
GLOBAL HEALTH ISSUES IN MICROBIOLOGY FOCUSING ON EASTERN
EUROPE AND THE CAUCASUS REGION – STUDENT SESSION**

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

ABSTRACT & THESIS

GEORGIA, TBILISI NOVEMBER 24, 2025

THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE - MODERN CHALLENGES AND
GLOBAL HEALTH ISSUES IN MICROBIOLOGY FOCUSING ON EASTERN
EUROPE AND THE CAUCASUS REGION – STUDENT SESSION

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

ABSTRACT & THESIS

GEORGIA, TBILISI NOVEMBER 24, 2025

TBILISI 2025

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

Organizers:

MTÜ The International Center for Research Education & Training. (Estonia, Tallinn).

Tbilisi State Medical University, Students' Scientific Society (Georgia, Tbilisi).

ESCMID - European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (Georgia, Tbilisi).

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Organizing Committee	04
Scientific Committee	05
Publishing Committee	06
Editorial Board	07
Program at a Glance	08
Abstracts and Theses	11

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Bachana Aptsiauri

Vice-President Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Ivliane Surmava

President, Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Khatuna Gachechildaze

Associate Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Lia Gubeladze

Assistant Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Maia Mikeladze

Assistant Professor, Microbiology Departmen, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Nikoloz Kajaia

Vice-President Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Tamar Didbaridze

Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Khatuna Gachechiladze

Associate Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Lia Gubeladze

Assistant Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Maia Mikeladze

Assistant Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Nikoloz Kajaia

Vice-President Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Tamar Didbaridze

Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

PUBLISHING COMMITTEE

Bachana Aptsiauri

Vice-President Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Namig Isazade

IRETC MTÜ, Shareholder. (Estonia, Tbilisi)

Nikoloz Kajaia

Vice-President Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

EDITORIAL BOARD

Khatuna Gachechildaze

Associate Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Lia Gubeladze

Assistant Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Maia Mikeladze

Assistant Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Nikoloz Kajaia

Vice-President Students Scientific Society of Tbilisi State Medical University.

Tamar Didbaridze

Professor, Microbiology Department, Tbilisi State Medical University.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

PROGRAM AT A GLANCE

12:00- 12:15	Opening and Greetings of The Students and Young Scientists Session
12:15 – 12:22	Innovation Treatment with Targeted Therapy in CML with Imatinib: A Retrospective Hospital-Based Study in Georgia. Dali Kekelidze - PhD Student in Life Sciences, Ilia State University Supervisor: Prof. Nina Lolashvili, MD, PhD - Department of Hematology, Tbilisi State Medical University
12:25 – 12:32	Autoimmune Activation After Previous Brucellosis: Evidence from Patients in the Caucasus Region Sabina Hasanzade ; Sina Seyyedhamzeh ; Bakhshiyeva Ulkar – Bachelor Students at Faculty of General Medicine in Azerbaijan Medical University (AMU), Baku, Azerbaijan Supervisor: Ass. Prof. Hayat Aliyeva , Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology, Azerbaijan Medical University
12:35 – 12:42	Efficacy of Bacteriophage Therapy in Managing Antibiotic-Resistant and Antibiotic- Allergic Ocular Infections Gigi Gorgadze - Ophthalmology Resident at Chicua Medical Center MZERA Supervisor : Prof. Nino Karanadze , Department of ophthalmology , Tbilisi State Medical University
12:45 – 12:52	Susceptibility of Clinical Acinetobacter baumannii Isolates to Cefiderocol and Colistin in a Lithuanian Hospital Artemij Morozov¹, Vizujė Greta² , Sauliūnė Kotryna² , Kirkliauskienė Agnė³ - Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania - Microbiology Laboratory, Republic Vilnius University Hospital, Vilnius, Lithuania - Department of Physiology, Biochemistry, Microbiology, and Laboratory Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

12:55 – 13:02	Hospital-acquired infections in Lithuania: Etiology and characteristics with a focus on intensive care units (2020-2024) Elzė Vaitkevičiūtė¹, Agnė Kirkliauskienė², Rolanda Valintėlienė^{1,3} - Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania - Department of Physiology, Biochemistry, Microbiology, and Laboratory Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania - The Institute of Hygiene, Vilnius, Lithuania
13:05 – 13:12	Seasonal Influenza Trends and Vaccination Mariam Umekashvili – Public Health Student , Tbilisi State Medical University Supervisor: Lia Gumbaridze – Assistant Professor Department of Public Health Management, Policy and Economics.
13:15 – 13:22	Antimicrobial Resistance Profile of Pseudomonas aeruginosa in Vilnius City Clinical Hospital, Vilnius, Lithuania Nanda Shajan¹, Miciulevičienė Jolanta², Kučinskienė Živilė³, Kirkliauskienė Agnė³ – Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania – Laboratory Medicine Centre, Vilnius City Clinical Hospital, Vilnius, Lithuania – Department of Physiology, Biochemistry, Microbiology, and Laboratory Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania
13:25 – 13:32	Current Use of “Healthy” Bacteria (Probiotics) in Allergy - A Narrative Review Mohamed Mahdey - Medical Student , Ilia state university Supervisor : Nino Didbaridze -Assistant Professor in the Department of Immunology , Tbilisi State Medical University
13:35 – 13:42	The Silent Pandemic Caused by the Spread of Multidrug resistant Strains of Bacteria Nikoloz Khukhunaishvili - Medical Student , American MD Program , Tbilisi State Medical University Supervisor: Tamar Didbaridze – Professor , Head of the Microbiology Department , Tbilisi State Medical University.
13:45 – 13:52	Antibiotic Resistance Awareness Among Medical Students in Georgia: A Cross-Sectional Study Mariam Varazashvili - Medical Student , Caucasus University Supervisor: Ana T. , Department of radiology, “Todua clinic”, Tbilisi, Georgia

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

14:10 – 14:40	<p>Poster Session</p> <p><i>Phage Therapy of Purulent Wounds in Diabetic and Practically Healthy Patients</i> Irakli Mishidze^{1,2}, Gela Arabidze³, Nina Chanishvili^{1,3} 1- New Vision University, 2 - Eliava Phage Therapy Center, 3- G. Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology</p> <p><i>Exploring the Therapeutic Potential of the Urine-Isolated E. coli Phages Under Variable pH Conditions</i> Tamar Tatrishvili^{1,2}, Giorgi Tchelidze^{1,2}, Tamar Barbakadze², Nato Kotaria³, Adam Kotorashvili³, Nina Chanishvili¹ 1 - G. Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology & Virology, Tbilisi, Georgia; 2 - Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia; 3 - NCDC, Tbilisi, Georgia</p> <p><i>Newly isolated phages against the emerging MDR Stenotrophomonas maltophilia strains</i> Davit Lazviashvili^{1,2}, Nina Chanishvili¹, Nata Bakuradze^{1,3} 1 - Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology, Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology. Tbilisi, Georgia 2 - Faculty of Natural Sciences and Medicine, Ilia State University. Tbilisi, Georgia 3 - Davit Tvildiani Medical University. Tbilisi, Georgia</p> <p><i>Biological and antibacterial properties of the bacteriophage vb_Ef_TGZ1 targeting Enterococcus spp. isolated from the urological samples</i> Teona Kheladze¹, Giorgi Tchelidze¹, Nino Grdzlishvili^{1,2}, Nata Bakuradze^{1,4}, Nato Kotaria³, Adam Kotorashvili³, Nina Chanishvili¹ 1- G.Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology, Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology - Ilia State University, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Medicine - National Center For Disease, Control and Public Health - Davit Tvildiani Medical University</p> <p><i>Study Of The Use of Antibiotics In the Poultry Sector In Georgia 2021-2023</i> Dimitri Gogebashvili - PhD Student in Life Sciences , New Vision University Supervisor: Nina Chanishvili - Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology, Georgia; Anders Miki BOJESEN – University of Copenhagen, Denmark;</p>
---------------	---

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

ABSTRACTS AND THESES

INNOVATION TREATMENT WITH TARGETED THERAPY IN CML WITH IMATINIB: A RETROSPECTIVE HOSPITAL-BASED STUDY IN GEORGIA

Dali Kekelidze¹, Nina Lolashvili²

¹School of Natural Sciences and Medicine, Ilia State University, Georgia

²Department of Hematology, Tbilisi State Medical University, Georgia

Introduction: Chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) was the first oncological disease for which targeted therapy—specifically, tyrosine kinase inhibitor (TKI) Imatinib—was introduced. While Imatinib has transformed the treatment paradigm for CML, real-world data remain limited, particularly in developing countries. This study aimed to evaluate clinical, laboratory, and cytogenetic outcomes in CML patients treated with Imatinib and to identify potential prognostic risk factors.

Methods: A retrospective hospital-based study was conducted among 219 patients with CML treated at LTD Medinvest Institute of Hematology and Transfusiology, Georgia, between 2003 and 2018. Clinical-laboratory parameters, cytogenetic responses, and survival outcomes were analyzed. Kaplan–Meier survival analysis was applied, and treatment responses were assessed at 3, 6, and 12 months.

Results: Of the 219 patients, 30 (13.7%) died during the study period. After three months of therapy, hematological indicators improved in all patients. No significant differences in relative risk were observed across subgroups. At six months, 82.3% achieved cytogenetic improvement, increasing slightly to 83.5% after twelve months. Kaplan–Meier analysis revealed higher survival rates in patients who began treatment during the chronic phase compared to those in the accelerated phase. Treatment outcomes did not significantly differ between patients receiving 400 mg and 600 mg doses of Imatinib.

Conclusion: Imatinib demonstrated substantial effectiveness in the management of CML, leading to improved hematological and cytogenetic responses and a reduction in fatal outcomes. These findings reinforce the importance of timely diagnosis and initiation of targeted therapy, while also highlighting the need for broader access to advanced treatment modalities in resource-limited settings.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

EFFICACY OF BACTERIOPHAGE THERAPY IN MANAGING ANTIBIOTIC-RESISTANT AND ANTIBIOTIC-ALLERGIC OCULAR INFECTIONS

Nino Karanadze^{1,2}, Gigi Gorgadze³

¹Tbilisi State Medical University

²LIONS Eye Diabetic Clinic – Georgia

³Chichua Medical Center MZERA

Introduction: The rising prevalence of antibiotic resistance and antibiotic hypersensitivity has created major challenges in the management of ocular infections. Allergic reactions to antibiotics may range from mild dermatological manifestations to severe anaphylaxis, complicating therapy.

Meanwhile, resistance mechanisms, including target modification, enzymatic degradation (e.g., β -lactamases), altered membrane permeability, and efflux pump activity have reduced the effectiveness of conventional antimicrobials worldwide. In ophthalmology, these factors significantly limit treatment options. Since 2000, the Department of Eye Diseases at Tbilisi State Medical University has introduced the use of Pio-bacteriophage for patients with antibiotic-resistant or antibiotic-allergic eye diseases, as well as for cases unresponsive to prior antibiotic therapy. Bacteriophage therapy offers notable advantages over antibiotics, including pathogen specificity, adaptability, minimal risk of systemic side effects or allergic reactions, natural biodegradability, and a lower potential for inducing resistance. The present study aimed to evaluate treatment outcomes of Pio-bacteriophage in ocular infections.

Methods: Pio-bacteriophage, produced at the George Eliava Institute of Bacteriophage, Microbiology and Virology, which targets *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Proteus* species, was administered via topical instillation, application, and nasolacrimal duct irrigation. Patient data were retrospectively collected from medical histories and follow-up records.

Results: Seventy-nine patients were identified: 30 with chronic dacryocystitis, 27 with infectious-allergic conjunctivitis, and 22 with blepharitis. Clinical improvement, including symptom resolution and full recovery, was documented in 61 of 79 cases.

Conclusion: The findings support the clinical efficacy and therapeutic value of Pio-bacteriophage as an alternative treatment for ocular infections where antibiotics are contraindicated or ineffective. Its additional benefits further highlight its potential role in modern ophthalmic practice.

SUSCEPTIBILITY OF CLINICAL ACINETOBACTER BAUMANNII ISOLATES TO CEFIDEROCOL AND COLISTIN IN A LITHUANIAN HOSPITAL

Artemij Morozov¹, Vizujė Greta², Sauliūnė Kotryna², Kirkliauskienė Agnė³

¹Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

²Microbiology Laboratory, Republic Vilnius University Hospital, Vilnius, Lithuania

³Department of Physiology, Biochemistry, Microbiology, and Laboratory Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

Introduction: *Acinetobacter baumannii* has become a major cause of healthcare-associated infections, associated with high morbidity and mortality. Its management is complicated by persistent multidrug resistance, particularly to carbapenems (Zarrilli et al., 2013). The declining efficacy of commonly used antibiotics has renewed reliance on colistin; however, resistance to this agent is increasingly reported (Buchhorn de Freitas & Hartwig, 2022). Cefiderocol demonstrates potent activity against most Gram-negative pathogens, including carbapenem- and colistin-resistant *A. baumannii*, yet emerging resistance and heteroresistance have also been observed (Sato & Yamawaki, 2019). This study aimed to determine the susceptibility of clinical *A. baumannii* strains to cefiderocol and colistin.

Methods: *A. baumannii* strains were collected in 2022, 2023, and up to September 2025, and stored at $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The collected specimens were categorized into four groups: blood, respiratory tract, skin and soft tissue, and urine. Clinical isolates of *A. baumannii* were identified using the MALDI-TOF VITEK® MS Microbial Identification System (bioMérieux, France). All stored strains were inoculated onto Brain Heart Infusion agar (Liofilchem®, Italy) and aerobically incubated for 24 h at $35 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. A 0.5 McFarland standard suspension of each strain was prepared and inoculated onto Mueller–Hinton agar (Bio-Rad, France). Susceptibility to cefiderocol was determined using the gradient diffusion method (MTS™ cefiderocol FDC 0.016–256 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$; Liofilchem®, Italy). The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for colistin (polymyxin E) was determined using the broth microdilution method with ComASP™ Colistin plates (Liofilchem®, Italy), containing wells with serial two-fold dilutions of the antibiotic (0.25–16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Both Petri dishes and microdilution plates were incubated at $35 \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 18 ± 2 hours. Results were interpreted according to the recommendations of the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST, version 15.0). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC® 27853™ was used as the quality control strain (EUCAST, 2025).

Results: A total of 159 *A. baumannii* isolates, isolated from patients aged 18 to 90 years, were included in the study. Colistin susceptibility was assessed in 116 of these isolates, revealing that 26.7% (n=43) of the tested strains were resistant to this antimicrobial. Cefiderocol resistance was observed in 16.4% (n=26) of the isolates. Furthermore, 16.4% of the strains demonstrated MICs

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

**Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region**

between 1–2 mg/L, suggesting the acquisition of resistance mechanisms that may compromise clinical efficacy.

Conclusion: This study demonstrated notable resistance to cefiderocol (16.4%) and colistin (26.7%) among clinical *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates. The presence of strains with elevated cefiderocol MIC values indicates emerging resistance mechanisms that may compromise treatment efficacy. Ongoing surveillance is essential to guide effective antimicrobial stewardship and infection control strategies.

STUDY OF THE USE OF ANTIBIOTICS IN THE POULTRY SECTOR IN GEORGIA 2021-2023

Dimitri Gogebashvili^{1,2,6,8}, Nina Chansihvili^{1,2,6,7}, Anders Miki Bojesen³,
Mariam Mchedlishvili⁴, Zurab Rukhadze⁵, Irakli Tsikhelashvili⁵, Nandini Sreenivasan⁶,
Rodolphe Mader⁶, Maia Beruashvili^{1,6,8}

¹Ministry of Environment and Agriculture, Georgia;

²New Vision University, Georgia;

³University of Copenhagen, Denmark;

⁴ANOVA, Georgia;

⁵NFA, Georgia;

⁶ICARS, Denmark;

⁷Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology, Georgia;

⁸European University, Georgia.

Introduction: In May 2015, the 68th World Health Assembly adopted the "Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance." The WHO urged the member countries to draft and implement a National Action Plan (NAP) to contain the development of antimicrobial resistance. In Georgia, the NAP was developed in 2017, to strengthen surveillance and research related to AMR [1]. This strategy was implemented in a coordinated manner by the Ministry of Health (MOH) and the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Agriculture (MEPA). Significant progress has been made in healthcare, but the extent of antibiotic use in the veterinary field remains questionable. We evaluated national antimicrobial use (AMU) in the veterinary sector, using the poultry sector as a case study. Our analysis draws on multiple data sources and examines how the National Action Plan (NAP) regulates AMU in Georgia.

Methods: We estimated AMU from 2021 to 2023 by (i) collecting official AMU data from government sources including the National Statistics Office of Georgia (NSOG) and the National Food Agency (NFA), (ii) sending a questionnaire on antimicrobial sales to 12 major distributors of veterinary products, and (iii) collecting AMU data from two large commercial poultry farms in Georgia.

Results: Data from the NSOG provided an overall estimate of the amount spent on imported and exported antibiotics for the following antimicrobial classes: penicillins, tetracyclines, sulphonamides, chloramphenicol, erythromycins, fluoroquinolones, their derivatives, and antibiotics belonging to other classes. The largest amount was spent on the import of tetracyclines. There was no indication of the volumes or whether antibiotics were intended for humans or animals. According to data from the NFA, the quantities of antibiotics sold in Georgia were 11,300 kg, 7,052 kg, and 9,927 kg in 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively. Of note, reporting on antibiotic sales from distributors is not mandatory. This voluntary approach opens the possibility of answering questions carelessly without relying on real figures. Only one distributor

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

**Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region**

provided detailed information in response to our survey. The distributor reported selling antibiotics from all classes as follows: 148 tons in 2020, 91 tons in 2021, and 79 tons in 2022. These volumes are significantly higher than the national estimates from the NFA. Neither the data provided by the NFA nor by the distributor companies were stratified by animal species, limiting the specificity of the analysis. Only the data provided directly from the farms enabled us to estimate the volume of antibiotics used during poultry rearing. Farm 1 used approximately 1,600 kg of tetracyclines per year for growth promotion, while Farm 2 used approximately 125 kg per year for the same purpose. The data on antibiotic use collected from two poultry farms shows that medium-sized farms use approximately 1,4-16 kg of colistin, 4.8 kg of sulfadiazine, 0.960kg of trimethoprim, and 0,5 kg of enrofloxacin. The total weight of different classes of antibiotics used per cycle is approximately 7.95 kg/cycle.

Conclusions: Our results suggest that the data based on voluntary reporting to the NFA, and indirectly to the World Animal Health Organization [2], is largely underestimated. We recommend improving the national monitoring system for AMU in the animal sector in Georgia by making it mandatory for distributors to provide their annual antimicrobial sales data. In addition, a representative farm-level study on AMU in Georgia is necessary to better understand how antibiotics are used for the main animal species to have more insights into NAP implementation.

PHAGE THERAPY OF PURULENT WOUNDS IN DIABETIC AND PRACTICALLY HEALTHY PATIENTS

Irakli Mishidze^{1,2}, Gela Arabidze³, Nina Chanishvili^{1,3}

¹New Vision University

²Eliava Phage Therapy Center

³G. Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology

Introduction: The rapidly rising trend of antibiotic resistance is one of the most critical global challenges in modern medicine. Treating chronic and purulent wounds caused by resistant microorganisms is particularly problematic. In diabetic patients, such infections often become severe, making traditional antibiotic therapy less effective. Against this background, bacteriophage therapy is considered a promising biological alternative, which is based on the use of specific bacteriophages, that induce bacterial lysis and promote the regeneration of damaged tissues. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of phage therapy alone, as well as in combination with antibiotic therapy, in the treatment of infected wounds in diabetic and practically healthy patients.

Methodology: The study was conducted in two groups: Group I – 14 diabetic patients with chronic purulent wounds caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Among them, 5 patients were treated with the bacteriophage preparation “Phago-Pyo” only, while 9 patients received combined therapy with the phage and the antibiotic moxifloxacin (400 mg/day orally, once daily). Group II – 11 practically healthy individuals with localized purulent lesions (e.g., post-traumatic infections, including suppurative lesions following minor burns). In this group, 4 patients were treated only with “Phago-Pyo,” while 7 patients received combined therapy with the phage and moxifloxacin (400 mg/day orally, once daily). Treatment was prescribed based on the results of phage- and antibiotic susceptibility tests. The bacteriophage preparation “Phago-Pyo” contains a combination of phages active against the common pathogens of purulent infections: *S. aureus*, *Streptococcus* spp., *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, and *Proteus mirabilis*. The preparation was used in two forms: Ointment form – applied topically to the wound surface (specially prepared based on the use of Phago-Pyo); Solution form – applied locally to the wound area as an aerosol. The treatment and observation period lasted for 3 months. Evaluation criteria: Therapeutic effectiveness was assessed according to the following parameters: Intensity of pain — measured by the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS); Dynamics of purulent exudate reduction — based on visual and clinical assessment; Speed of epithelialization — determined by the number of days to complete wound healing.

Results: The study revealed significant differences in treatment effectiveness between different modalities of phage therapy. In diabetic patients (n=14), positive dynamics were observed in 5 cases treated with phage alone. In contrast, among those receiving combined therapy (phage +

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

**Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region**

antibiotic), 9 patients showed marked clinical improvement within 14–21 days after treatment initiation, characterized by pain reduction, decreased purulent exudation, and accelerated epithelialization. In practically healthy patients (n=11), complete healing occurred in 4 patients treated with phage alone within 11–13 days, whereas in those treated with combined therapy, healing was achieved in 7 patients within 7–9 days. Pain intensity (VAS score) decreased by an average of 2–3 points in the combined therapy subgroups, reflecting a clear analgesic effect as perceived by the patients.

Conclusion: The presented preliminary findings indicate that, in the treatment of both diabetic and non-diabetic wounds, combined therapy (phage + antibiotic) is relatively more effective than phage therapy alone. In healthy wound cases, the duration of treatment was reduced by an average of 3–4 days with combined therapy.

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PROFILE OF PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA IN VILNIUS CITY CLINICAL HOSPITAL, VILNIUS, LITHUANIA

Nanda Shajan¹, Miciulevičienė Jolanta², Kučinskienė Živilė², Kirkliauskienė Agnė³

¹Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

²Laboratory Medicine Centre, Vilnius City Clinical Hospital, Vilnius, Lithuania

³Department of Physiology, Biochemistry, Microbiology, and Laboratory Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

Introduction: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is a motile, nonfermenting, Gram-negative opportunistic pathogen that causes a range of healthcare-associated infections, including pneumonia, bloodstream and urinary tract infections, and wound infections. Its ability to form biofilms, adapt to environmental changes, and develop both intrinsic and acquired resistance makes treatment challenging. Traditional antibiotics are increasingly compromised by the development of multidrug resistant strains, making continuous monitoring essential. This study aimed to evaluate the susceptibility of clinical *P. aeruginosa* isolates from the Vilnius City Clinical Hospital in Lithuania to commonly used antimicrobials. Aim. This study aimed to determine the susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* strains to some antimicrobials.

Methods: Clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* were collected from patients at Vilnius City Clinical Hospital (510-bed regional hospital) in Vilnius, Lithuania, between 2023 and 2024, with ethics committee approval. All consecutive adult patients (≥ 18 years) with *P. aeruginosa* isolated from clinical specimens were included, while repeated isolates from the same patient were excluded. Specimens were grouped into skin and soft tissue, blood, respiratory tract, urine, and other categories (including kidney stone, ear canal discharge, peritoneal cavity, and pus from the kidney). Isolates were identified using the MALDI-TOF VITEK® MS Microbial Identification System (bioMérieux, France). Antimicrobial resistance testing and result interpretation were performed using the disk diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar (Bio-Rad, France) following EUCAST 2024 guidelines. Resistancy of all isolates to amikacin (30 µg), aztreonam (30 µg), imipenem (10 µg), levofloxacin (5 µg), cefepime (30µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), piperacillin+tazobactam (30-6 µg), tobramycin (10 µg), meropenem (10 µg), and ceftazidime (10 µg) was tested using commercial discs (Liofilchem®, Italy). For quality control, *P. aeruginosa* ATCC® 27853™ was used (EUCAST, 2024).

Results: The study included 54 patients from whom *P. aeruginosa* was isolated in their specimens. 61.1% (n = 33) of the strains were isolated from skin and soft tissue samples. 50.0% of patients were male. The youngest study participant was 18 years old, and the oldest was 102 years old. The mean age of the participants was 69.3 years. Antimicrobial resistance testing of the isolates revealed common resistance patterns, with the highest resistance observed against imipenem (22.2%), levofloxacin (22.2%), and piperacillin-tazobactam (18.5%). In contrast, the

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

**Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region**

lowest resistance rates were observed for aztreonam (5.6%) and tobramycin (1.9%). Furthermore, the highest levels of intermediate susceptibility were observed for aztreonam (94.4%), ceftazidime (90.7%), ciprofloxacin (87.0%), and cefepime (87.0%). However, a significant number of *P. aeruginosa* isolates were susceptible to tobramycin (98.1%) and amikacin (96.3%).

Conclusion: Our results show that *P. aeruginosa* isolates were most resistant to imipenem, levofloxacin, and piperacillin-tazobactam, while remaining highly susceptible to tobramycin and amikacin. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing antimicrobial stewardship and routine susceptibility testing to guide effective treatment.

HOSPITAL-ACQUIRED INFECTIONS IN LITHUANIA: ETIOLOGY AND CHARACTERISTICS WITH A FOCUS ON INTENSIVE CARE UNITS (2020-2024)

Elzė Vaitkevičiūtė¹, Agnė Kirkliauskienė², Rolanda Valintėlienė^{1,3}

¹Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

²Department of Physiology, Biochemistry, Microbiology, and Laboratory Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

³The Institute of Hygiene, Vilnius, Lithuania

Introduction: Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), acquired during hospitalization or following medical procedures in healthcare facilities, remain a global challenge, leading to considerable morbidity, mortality, and higher healthcare costs (Voinea et al., 2025). HAIs cause about 40,000 deaths per year, with the rates reaching up to 25% in developing countries and 5-15% in developed ones (Lemiech-Mirsowska et al., 2021). Generally, the highest rates of HAIs are observed in intensive care units (ICUs) (Rangel et al., 2021). Limited data from Eastern Europe and the Caucasus make it difficult to develop effective infection control strategies for the region (Mgeladze et al., 2025).

Methodology: A descriptive epidemiological study was conducted. Data was obtained from the Institute of Hygiene electronic database for the period of 2020-2024, using HAIs point prevalence study reports and data from continuous HAIs surveillance in ICUs. The data was processed using Microsoft Excel, employing absolute numbers and calculating averages and percentages. The aim of the study was to evaluate the burden and etiology of hospital-acquired infections across Lithuanian hospitals, with a particular focus on intensive care units.

Results: Data from point prevalence studies show that the prevalence of HAIs in Lithuania between 2020 and 2024 ranged from 448 to 508 cases per year. The highest number of HAIs was recorded in 2022 (n = 508), while the lowest was in 2021 (n = 448). The average prevalence of HAIs among hospitalized patients was 3.9%. The highest rates were observed in intensive care (21.6%), geriatric (7.3%), and surgical (5.2%) units of acute care hospitals. Data from continuous surveillance in ICUs shows that over five years, the incidence of HAIs per 1,000 patient-days in ICUs fluctuated between 13.9 and 25.8 cases, with the highest rate observed in 2022 (25.8) and lowest in 2020 (13.9). A total of 88 deaths due to HAIs were reported in the ICUs, including 2 pediatric cases. The most common infections in ICUs were pneumonia (45.1%), urinary tract infections (17.6%), and bloodstream infections (11.1%). The leading pathogens in ICUs – *Acinetobacter baumannii* (14.8%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (11.1%), *Escherichia coli* (9.6%) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (6.7%).

Conclusion : The prevalence of HAIs in Lithuania was 3.9%. with most cases reported in ICUs. Pneumonia remained the dominant hospital-acquired infection in ICUs, followed by urinary tract and bloodstream infections. The most common pathogens of HAIs in ICUs were *A. baumannii*, *K. pneumoniae*, *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

AUTOIMMUNE ACTIVATION AFTER PREVIOUS BRUCELLOSIS: EVIDENCE FROM PATIENTS IN THE CAUCASUS REGION

Sina Seyyedhamzeh¹ Sabina Hasanzade², Bakhshiyeva Ulkar³

¹Faculty of General Medicine Azerbaijan Medical University (AMU), Baku, Azerbaijan

^{2,3}Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology, Azerbaijan Medical University (AMU), Baku, Azerbaijan.

Introduction: Brucellosis is a globally prevalent zoonotic infection caused by *Brucella* spp., with over two million new cases annually, predominantly affecting livestock-dependent regions. Transmission occurs mainly through contact with infected animals or unpasteurized dairy, leading to a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations from acute fever to chronic osteoarticular complications. The Caucasus region, particularly Georgia and Dagestan, remains a major endemic area, where underreporting and diagnostic challenges obscure the true disease burden. Emerging evidence suggests *Brucella* infection may trigger autoimmune responses, including the production of rheumatoid factor, antinuclear, and anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies, often mimicking autoimmune rheumatic diseases. This overlap complicates diagnosis and management, highlighting the need to elucidate the immunopathogenic mechanisms linking brucellosis and autoimmunity in endemic settings. Brucellosis has been associated with the activation of autoimmune phenomena, likely through a combination of immune dysregulation, molecular mimicry, and persistent inflammation, but direct causation of classic autoimmune diseases remains unproven.

Methods: Fifty-four patients with serologically confirmed brucellosis were evaluated. Serum *Brucella* IgM and IgG were quantified by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), and the Wright agglutination test confirmed diagnosis. ANA screening was performed using ELISA, with positive samples further characterized by indirect immunofluorescence to determine staining patterns. Descriptive statistics were applied, and correlations between ANA titers and *Brucella* serologic parameters were assessed using Spearman's test.

Results: ANA positivity was detected in 30 of 82 patients (36.5%), a prevalence significantly higher than reported in comparable studies on non-rheumatic cohorts. The predominant ANA pattern was granular (43.3%), followed by homogeneous (26.7%), nucleolar (13.3%), and reticular (10%); mixed patterns occurred in 6.7% of cases. Mean *Brucella* IgM and IgG concentrations among ANA-positive patients were 1.04 IU/mL and 3.25 IU/mL, respectively. Crucially, higher Wright agglutination titers frequently showed a positive association with stronger ANA reactivity ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a relationship between infection intensity and the magnitude of the autoimmune response.

Conclusion: The high frequency of ANA positivity (36.5%) in this patient cohort provides strong evidence that persistent *Brucella* infection is a significant trigger for systemic autoantibody

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

formation. These results underscore the critical role of infection-driven immune dysregulation—likely through mechanisms like molecular mimicry or polyclonal B-cell activation—in bridging infection and autoimmunity. This highlights the need for larger, controlled, and long-term studies to define the specific immunological mechanisms and determine the ultimate clinical impact of this high ANA prevalence on future autoimmune disease development in endemic areas.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

THE SILENT PANDEMIC CAUSED BY THE SPREAD OF MULTIDRUGRESISTANT STRAINS OF BACTERIA

Nikoloz Khukhunaishvili

Tbilisi State Medical University.

Introduction: Humanity is losing leverage (antibiotics) against infections caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Due to the increasing use of antibiotics, a large number of bacteria have become resistant to antibiotics. Unfortunately, this process is irreversible and progresses quite quickly. By 2050, if urgent measures are not taken, 10 million people will die annually from infections caused by the so-called “Super Bug”. That is, humanity will return to the era before antibiotics. The purpose of this project is to study the genome of “Super Bugs” and raise awareness among the population.

Methods: The study includes a laboratory data analysis, and a survey. Bacterial isolates were collected from four clinics in Georgia. Antimicrobial resistance gene content was examined by multiplex PCR, targeting plasmid-mediated AmpC and beta-lactamases, representing fifteen gene families. For the survey, questionnaire was made in Google Forms and was sent to the interviewees. Among the interviewees were medical students, students from other faculties, doctors, and individuals not involved in medicine. The questionnaire sought to assess respondents’ knowledge and awareness regarding multidrug-resistant bacterial strains.

Results: It was found that the 80% of respondents have taken an antibiotic at least once without doctor’s recommendation. 85% of the interviewees, including some medical professionals, is unaware of wide spread of multi resistant strains of bacteria and its implications. As part of the scientific project conducted by the US Walter Reed Army Institute of Research and the First University Clinic of TSMU, titled “Laboratory-Based Monitoring and Genetic Characterization of Antimicrobial-Resistant Bacteria in Georgia,” 168 samples laboratory data were analyzed and it became clear that “Superbugs” have plasmid genes (CTX-M-15, CTX-M-14, OXA-48, VIM, IMP). These genes cause their resistance to antibiotics and are activated differently in the human body and on agar plates, making it difficult to start an effective treatment.

Conclusion: Prevalence of multi resistant strains was observed in bacterial isolates found in Georgia. Detection of plasmid-related resistance genes indicates the high potential of horizontal spread of resistance and the danger of emergence of new “superbugs” in Georgia. Addressing the escalation of this issue requires strategies aimed at increasing public awareness and promoting the rational use of antibiotics.

EXPLORING THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF THE URINE-ISOLATED E. COLI PHAGES UNDER VARIABLE PH CONDITIONS

Tamar Tatrishvili^{1,2}, Giorgi Tchelidze^{1,2}, Tamar Barbakadze², Nato Kotaria³, Adam Kotorashvili³, Nina Chanishvili¹

¹G. Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology & Virology, Tbilisi, Georgia;

²Iliia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia;

³NCDC, Tbilisi, Georgia

Introduction: Urinary tract infections (UTIs) remain a major global public health concern, characterized by persistently high incidences, frequent recurrence, and significant healthcare burden. Recent global and regional analyses indicate that UTIs are among the most common bacterial infections worldwide, accounting for substantial numbers of outpatient visits and antibiotic prescriptions (He, Y., Zhao, J. et al., 2025). With this regard particular interest is drawn to the human microbiome and the role of the bacteriophages (phages) in maintaining of homeostasis in the urology tract. This field remains relatively underexplored but is believed to play a crucial role in maintaining host immunity and overall health. This study aimed to investigate activity of two phages, previously isolated from the human urine samples, under varying pH conditions that may arise in urine during different pathogenic changes.

Methods: Two phages were selected for the model experiments: vB-GrEc and vB-MEC4. Both phage belong to Myoviridae morphology type. Taxonomy analysis showed that these phages belong to Phylum Uroviricota, Class Caudoviricetes, but to different genera (phage vB-GrEc is attributed to genus Tequatrovirus, while phage MEC4 – to genus Felixounavirus). Phage vB_GrEc is genetically closely related to Escherichia phage 232Ecol030PP(PP355090), while phage vB-MEC4 showed high relatedness with Escherichia phage nataliec (MN850611).

Results: The phage activities were assessed in both environments. i.e. artificial urine and LB broth. The titer of phage vB-GrEc remained stable in artificial urine and LB broth at pH 5, 7, 9, & 11 during the whole observation period. However, its titer reduces 1 log at pH 3 after 24 h of observation both in artificial urine and for 2 logs in LB. In artificial urine the titer of phage vB-MEC4 dropped for 1 log at pH 3 already after 6 h of observation, the titer gradually decreased for 1 log after 24h and 48 h. The phage remained stable in artificial urine at pH 5, 7, 9 and 11. The same phage appeared to be susceptible at pH 3 in LB broth after 6 h of incubation, its titer dropped for 1 log at pH 5 after 48 h of observation. The both studied phages showed high resistance to pH conditions, except pH 3. Although the titers of the both phages dropped at pH 3 for 1-2 logs, their levels still remained high enough (10⁶ cfu/mL) to combat E.coli infection.

Conclusion: This fact indicates that the phages can be used for treatment of the E.coli infections even in those cases that may arise during severe systemic acidosis, such as diabetic ketoacidosis or metabolic acidosis and from other causes like severe diarrhea or starvation.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

NEWLY ISOLATED PHAGES AGAINST THE EMERGING MDR STENOTROPHOMONAS MALTOPHILIA STRAINS

Davit Lazviashvili^{1,2}, Nina Chanishvili¹, Nata Bakuradze^{1,3}

¹Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology, Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology. Tbilisi, Georgia

²Faculty of Natural Sciences and Medicine, Ilia State University. Tbilisi, Georgia

³Davit Tvildiani Medical University. Tbilisi, Georgia

Introduction: The World Health Organization currently lists *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* as an important Gram-negative multidrug-resistant nosocomial bacterial pathogen. Infections caused by this environmental and opportunistic intrinsically drug-resistant organism are of significant concern among the immunocompromised patient population and can lead to lethal outcomes. A few antibiotics, such as trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (TMP-SMX), are currently being successful against the *S. maltophilia* infections. The goal of our study was to isolate and study the therapeutic potential of bacteriophages targeting specifically clinically isolated *S. maltophilia*.

Methods: We have selected 10 clinical strains of *S. maltophilia* for isolation of the active phages from the waste waters of Tbilisi. Antibiotic susceptibility of the selected strains was performed using Kirby-Bauer method and their biochemical identification was performed via API 32 E. Enrichment method was used to isolate bacteriophages. Phage susceptibility of *S. maltophilia* strains was identified using spot-test assay. We have also studied the biofilm producing ability to select the most virulent multi-drug resistant and biofilm-forming strains, which were used then 24 h time-kill assay.

Results: We have isolated two phages active to *S. maltophilia* isolates - Vb_SM_MA and Vb_SM_GA. Based on the spot-test assay two *S. maltophilia* isolates were selected for further tests. These strains appeared positive for biofilm production and showed to be resistant towards all four antibiotics (cefiderocol, chloramphenicol, levofloxacin, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (TMP-SMX) used in the research. We have performed the time-kill assay to see the antibacterial activity of the isolated phages, which showed a 24 h lytic activity. Based on the time-kill assay results, it can be stated that the phage Vb_SM_GA exhibits strong antibacterial activity against one of the two selected bacterial isolates. The phage maintains low bacterial concentration compared to the control group for 24 hours when the MOI (Multiplicity of Infection) = 1, and for 20 hours when the MOI = 0.1.

Conclusion: The limited scope of this study does not allow to draw out definitive conclusions; nevertheless, the obtained results indicate that the phage Vb_SM_GA shows high potential for future application against emerging *S. maltophilia* strains. However, further investigation of its biological and genetic characteristics is required, which is planned for the subsequent stages of this study.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

BIOLOGICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL PROPERTIES OF THE BACTERIOPHAGE VB_EF_TGZ1 TARGETING ENTEROCOCCUS SPP. ISOLATED FROM THE UROLOGICAL SAMPLES

Teona Kheladze¹, Giorgi Tchelidze¹, Nino Grdzlishvili^{1,2}, Nata Bakuradze^{1,4},
Nato Kotaria³, Adam Kotorashvili³, Nina Chanishvili¹

¹G.Eliava Institute of Bacteriophages, Microbiology and Virology, Laboratory of Microbial Biotechnology

²Ilia State University, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Medicine

³National Center For Disease, Control and Public Health

⁴Davit Tvildiani Medical University

Introduction: Enterococcus is a common cause of nosocomial infections, such as catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI), wound and blood infections. They show intrinsic resistance to commonly used antibiotics such as beta-lactams and easily acquire resistance to other antimicrobial agents, such as the vancomycin. Although research is actively being conducted to discover and synthesize new antibiotics, there is a risk, that after some time, bacteria will develop resistance to these new agents as well. Therefore, alternative options for treatment such as phage therapy are also considered as alternatives. The aim of this research was to find and study phages active against Enterococcus spp.

Methods: Nineteen (19) bacterial isolates related to Enterococcus spp were derived from the urine samples. They were tested for susceptibility to antibiotics according to Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. Biofilm forming ability of the isolates were also studied. Bacteriophage active against Enterococcus spp. was isolated using enrichment technique and its morphology was examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The lytic activity against bacterial strains was assessed by determining their efficiency of plating (EOP). Biological characterization of the phage included evaluating its stability under different pH and temperature conditions. In addition, anti-biofilm properties of the phage was also studied in vitro using TSA broth as well as synthetic urine media to simulate urinary tract infections. Phage genome was sequenced and analyzed using relevant programs to determine its genetic composition.

Results: Two of the tested isolates, E. faecium 10 and E. faecalis 61, were found to be multidrug-resistant exhibiting resistance to several classes of antimicrobials. Sixteen out of these nineteen isolates formed biofilms. Particularly, strong biofilms were produced by five strains: E. faecalis 9, E. faecium 10, E. faecium 71, E. faecalis 86 & E. faecalis 90. The bacteriophage vb_Ef_TGZ1 (TGZ1) was isolated from the sewage water in Tbilisi. It belongs to the Siphoviridae morphological group. Genetic analysis revealed TGZ1 to have a double- stranded linear DNA belonging to the class of Caudaviricetes, genus Saphexavirus. TGZ1 demonstrated lytic activity against multidrug-resistant isolate E. faecium 10. The phage activity was stable between 4°C-

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

**Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region**

55°C after 1.5 hours of incubation. Its titer decreased significantly at 65°C and was not detectable at 70°C. The optimal activity of TGZ1 was observed at pH7 and in mildly alkaline conditions. TGZ1 inhibited biofilm formation by *E. faecium* 4 and exhibited stable lytic activity in both broth and synthetic urine.

Conclusion: considering the biological and genetic properties, lytic activity and inhibition of the biofilm formation revealed by the phage TGZ1, suggest that this phage represents a promising agent to be used in phage therapy; however, additional studies are required to study its antibacterial effectiveness as well as safety.

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AWARENESS AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS IN GEORGIA: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

Mariami Varazashvili¹, Ana Tvalavadze²

¹Caucasus university, Tbilisi, Georgia

²Department of radiology, “Todua clinic”, Tbilisi, Georgia

Introduction: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major global health problem, causing more than thirty-five thousand deaths each year in the U.S. alone due to infections that do not respond to treatment. The World Health Organization has emphasized that without urgent action, AMR could lead to ten million deaths per year by 2050. Medical students, who are the future prescribers are important in tackling this issue. However, gaps in knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward antibiotics and resistance persist among medical students globally. The purpose of this research was to evaluate how well second-year medical students recognize and comprehend the issue of antibiotic resistance.

Methods: We carried out a cross-sectional survey in May 2025 among second-year students from two medical universities in Tbilisi. A questionnaire with twenty-four questions assessed knowledge (ten), attitudes (seven), and practices (seven). In total, two hundred eighteen students participated. Data were analyzed with SPSS version 26. Chi-square tests were applied, with $p < 0.05$ taken as significant.

Results: Among Georgian respondents, 78% identified AMR as a major global health concern. Just 41% of students recognized that antibiotics are not effective against viral infections. Higher numbers were reported among Indian (56,3%) and Saudi (73,2%) medical students. 65% reported self-medicating with antibiotics at least once. Students with earlier lessons on antibiotic use showed higher knowledge scores. In addition, most students (89%) felt their studies didn't teach enough about antimicrobial resistance and were interested about formal antimicrobial stewardship training.

Conclusion: Although awareness of AMR is relatively high, critical knowledge gaps and risky behaviors persist among second-year medical students. Integrating targeted AMR education into the medical curriculum is essential to cultivate responsible prescribing behaviors and mitigate the global AMR crisis.

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Dali Kekelidze, Nina Lolashvili INNOVATION TREATMENT WITH TARGETED THERAPY IN CML WITH IMATINIB: A RETROSPECTIVE HOSPITAL-BASED STUDY IN GEORGIA	11
Nino Karanadze, Gigi Gorgadze EFFICACY OF BACTERIOPHAGE THERAPY IN MANAGING ANTIBIOTIC-RESISTANT AND ANTIBIOTIC-ALLERGIC OCULAR INFECTIONS	12
Artemij Morozov, Vizujė Greta, Sauliūnė Kotryna, Kirkliauskienė Agnė SUSCEPTIBILITY OF CLINICAL ACINETOBACTER BAUMANNII ISOLATES TO CEFIDEROCOL AND COLISTIN IN A LITHUANIAN HOSPITAL	13
Dimitri Gogebashvili, Nina Chansihvili, Anders Miki Bojesen, Mariam Mchedlishvili, Zurab Rukhadze, Irakli Tsikhelashvili. Nandini Sreenivasan, Rodolphe Mader, Maia Beruashvili STUDY OF THE USE OF ANTIBIOTICS IN THE POULTRY SECTOR IN GEORGIA 2021-2023	15
Irakli Mishidze, Gela Arabidze, Nina Chanishvili PHAGE THERAPY OF PURULENT WOUNDS IN DIABETIC AND PRACTICALLY HEALTHY PATIENTS	17
Nanda Shajan, Miciulevičienė Jolanta, Kučinskienė Živilė, Kirkliauskienė Agnė ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PROFILE OF PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA IN VILNIUS CITY CLINICAL HOSPITAL, VILNIUS, LITHUANIA	19
Elzė Vaitkevičiūtė, Agnė Kirkliauskienė, Rolanda Valintėlienė HOSPITAL-ACQUIRED INFECTIONS IN LITHUANIA: ETIOLOGY AND CHARACTERISTICS WITH A FOCUS ON INTENSIVE CARE UNITS (2020-2024)	21
Sina Seyyedhamzeh, Sabina Hasanzade, Bakhshiyeva Ulkar AUTOIMMUNE ACTIVATION AFTER PREVIOUS BRUCELLOSIS: EVIDENCE FROM PATIENTS IN THE CAUCASUS REGION	22
Nikoloz Khukhunaishvili THE SILENT PANDEMIC CAUSED BY THE SPREAD OF MULTIDRUGRESISTANT STRAINS OF BACTERIA	24
Tamar Tatrishvili, Giorgi Tchelidze, Tamar Barbakadze, Nato Kotaria, Adam Kotorashvili, Nina Chanishvili EXPLORING THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF THE URINE-ISOLATED E. COLI PHAGES UNDER VARIABLE PH CONDITIONS	25

Students and Young Scientists Session
TSMU, Administrative Building, Conference Hall III
November 24, 2025

Modern Challenges and Global Health
Issues in Microbiology Focusing on Eastern Europe
and The Caucasus Region

Davit Lazviashvili, Nina Chanishvili, Nata Bakuradze NEWLY ISOLATED PHAGES AGAINST THE EMERGING MDR STENOTROPHOMONAS MALTOPHILIA STRAINS	26
Teona Kheladze, Giorgi Tchelidze, Nino Grdzlishvili, Nata Bakuradze, Nato Kotaria, Adam Kotorashvili, Nina Chanishvili BIOLOGICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL PROPERTIES OF THE BACTERIOPHAGE VB_EF_TGZ1 TARGETING ENTEROCOCCUS SPP. ISOLATED FROM THE UROLOGICAL SAMPLES	27
Mariami Varazashvili, Ana Tvalavadze ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AWARENESS AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS IN GEORGIA: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY	29

Organizers of the conference:

MTÜ. The International Center for Research Education & Training. (Estonia, Tallinn).

Tbilisi State Medical University (Georgia, Tbilisi).

©**Publisher:** NGO International Center for Research, Education and Training.

MTÜ Rahvusvaheline Teadus-, Haridus- ja Koolituskeskus.

Management Board Member: Seyfulla Isayev.

©**Editorial office:** Kesklinna linnaosa, Vesivärava tn 50-301, 10152, Tallinn, Estonia.

©**Typography:** NGO International Research, Education & Training Center. The Baltic Scientific Journals.

Registered address: Kesklinna linnaosa, Vesivärava tn 50-301, 10152, Tallinn, Estonia.

Telephones: +994 55 241 70 12; +994 51 864 88 94; +994 70 375 70 12;

Website:

E-mail: gulustanbssjar@gmail.com, sc.mediagroup2017@gmail.com

E-ISBN:

DOI suffix:

THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE - MODERN CHALLENGES AND
GLOBAL HEALTH ISSUES IN MICROBIOLOGY FOCUSING ON EASTERN
EUROPE AND THE CAUCASUS REGION – STUDENT SESSION

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

ABSTRACT & THESIS

GEORGIA, TBILISI NOVEMBER 24, 2025